

LINEAR COMBINATIONS OF DIRICHLET SERIES ASSOCIATED WITH THE THUE-MORSE SEQUENCE

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Abstract

In this paper we study sums of Dirichlet series whose coefficients are terms of the Thue-Morse sequence and variations thereof. We find closed-form expressions for such sums in terms of known constants and functions including the Riemann zeta function and the Dirichlet eta function using elementary methods.

– Dedicated to Walter Alexandre.

1. Introduction

Let t_n denote the binary digit sum of the positive integer n modulo 2, in other words, the n^{th} element of the Thue-Morse sequence $(t_n)_{n \geq 0}$, which begins

$$0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1, \dots$$

This sequence was first considered by Prouhet [10] and has applications in many different fields of mathematics (see for instance Allouche and Shallit [8] for a detailed overview). A popular variant is the ± 1 Thue-Morse sequence, denoted by ε_n and defined as $((-1)^{t_n})_{n \geq 0}$. Dirichlet series associated with ε_n have been widely studied during the past years, in particular $\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\varepsilon_n}{n^s}$ and $\sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{\varepsilon_n}{(n+1)^s}$, which converge for $\Re(s) > 1$. Allouche and Cohen [3] continued the series analytically and gave the functional equation

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{\varepsilon_n}{(n+1)^s} = \sum_{k \geq 1} 2^{-s-k} \binom{s+k-1}{k} \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{\varepsilon_n}{(n+1)^{s+k}},$$

and showed that it admits non-trivial zeros at $s = (2k\pi i)/\log 2$ for any integer k . The series $\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\varepsilon_n}{n^s}$ is continued in a similar manner, yielding a set of non-trivial zeros at $s = i\pi(2k+1)/\log 2$ (although as noted by Allouche [2], the question of whether these are *all* the non-trivial zeros is still an open one). These results were

then further extended by Allouche, Mendès France and Peyrière [5] to d -automatic sequences, for $d \geq 2$. Furthermore, Allouche and Cohen [3] and Alkauskas [1] have noticed that the two series above are related through the identity

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{\varepsilon_n}{(n+1)^s} = \frac{1-2^s}{1+2^s} \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\varepsilon_n}{n^s}.$$

Since then, these series have been used in various contexts. For instance, Allouche and Cohen [3] used the derivative of $\sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{\varepsilon_n}{(n+1)^s}$ at $s = 0$ to give an alternative proof of the Woods-Robbins product,

$$\prod_{n \geq 0} \left(\frac{2n+1}{2n+2} \right)^{\varepsilon_n} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2},$$

which has been extended to many different types of infinite products (see Allouche, Cohen, Mendès France and Shallit [4], Allouche and Sondow [9], Allouche, Riasat and Shallit [6] and Tóth [12] for example).

Series involving the b -ary sum-of-digits function $s_b(n)$ have also been studied. A classic example is

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{s_b(n)}{n(n+1)} = \frac{b}{b-1} \log b,$$

which was proved by Shallit [11], while other identities such as

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{s_2(n)(2n+1)}{n^2(n+1)^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{9}$$

are due to Allouche and Shallit [7].

1.1. Scope of This Paper

No closed-form expression is currently known for Dirichlet series involving only t_n and t_{n-1} and combinations thereof in terms of known constants and functions. In this paper, we provide such closed forms and give a formula for generating similar linear combinations. A few examples are

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{5t_{n-1} + 3t_n}{n^2} = \frac{2\pi^2}{3},$$

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{9t_{n-1} + 7t_n}{n^3} = 8\zeta(3).$$

Then, we extend our results to combinations of sequences involving different alphabets $\{a, b\}$ along the Thue-Morse sequence, that is, sequences with the substitutions

$0 \rightarrow a$ and $1 \rightarrow b$ over t_n , with $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$. An example is

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{17q_{n-1} + 15r_n}{n^4} = 16\eta(4),$$

where $\eta(s)$ denotes the alternating zeta function $\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s}$ and q_n and r_n denote the sequences defined respectively by $\{-\sqrt{2}, 1 - \sqrt{2}\}$ and $\{\frac{17\sqrt{2}-2}{15}, \frac{17\sqrt{2}+13}{15}\}$ along the Thue-Morse sequence.

2. Linear Combinations

Throughout the remainder of this paper, we shall use the following notation:

$$f(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\varepsilon_{n-1}}{n^s}, \quad g(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\varepsilon_n}{n^s}, \quad \varphi(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{t_{n-1}}{n^s}, \quad \gamma(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{t_n}{n^s}.$$

We begin this section by recalling a result on Dirichlet series whose sign alternates following the Thue-Morse sequence, originally due to Allouche and Cohen [3] and already mentioned in the introduction.

Lemma 1. *For all $s \in \mathbb{C}$ with $\Re(s) > 1$,*

$$f(s) = \frac{1 - 2^s}{1 + 2^s} g(s).$$

While Allouche and Cohen’s proof involves the analytic continuations of f and g , a simpler proof was proposed by Alkauskas [1] in 2001 that we cannot resist replicating here. This proof relies only on the fact that every positive integer n can be uniquely represented as the product $2^k(2m + 1)$ for $k \geq 0$ and $m \geq 0$.

Proof of Lemma 1 ([1]). We have

$$f(s) = \sum_{k \geq 0, m \geq 0} \frac{\varepsilon_{2^k(2m+1)-1}}{2^{ks}(2m+1)^s} = \sum_{k \geq 0, m \geq 0} \frac{(-1)^k \varepsilon_m}{2^{ks}(2m+1)^s} = \frac{2^s}{2^s + 1} \sum_{m \geq 0} \frac{\varepsilon_m}{(2m+1)^s}.$$

Now we know that

$$\sum_{m \geq 0} \frac{\varepsilon_m}{(2m+1)^s} = \sum_{m \geq 1} \frac{\varepsilon_m}{(2m)^s} - \sum_{m \geq 1} \frac{\varepsilon_m}{m^s},$$

by splitting $\sum_{m \geq 1} \frac{\varepsilon_m}{m^s}$ into even and odd indexes and using the fact that $\varepsilon_{2m} = \varepsilon_m$ and $\varepsilon_{2m+1} = -\varepsilon_m$. The proof follows naturally. □

We note that one could also evaluate $g(s)$ in the same manner, thus yielding a unified proof of Lemma 1. This is left as an exercise for the reader.

Corollary 1. *For any holomorphic functions u and v , we have*

$$u(s)\varphi(s) + v(s)\gamma(s) = \frac{u(s) + v(s)}{2}\zeta(s) - \frac{f(s)}{2} \left(u(s) + v(s) \frac{1 + 2^s}{1 - 2^s} \right).$$

Proof. Using Lemma 1 together with $\varepsilon_n = 1 - 2t_n$, we have

$$\varphi(s) = \frac{1}{2}\zeta(s) - \frac{1}{2}f(s), \quad \gamma(s) = \frac{1}{2}\zeta(s) - \frac{1 + 2^s}{2(1 - 2^s)}f(s).$$

Now taking two holomorphic functions u and v , we quickly obtain the above expression for $u(s)\varphi(s) + v(s)\gamma(s)$. \square

We now have all the tools to establish our first result in this paper.

Theorem 1. *Let $\zeta(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} 1/n^s$ denote the Riemann zeta function defined for complex s with $\Re(s) > 1$. Then*

$$(2^s + 1)\varphi(s) + (2^s - 1)\gamma(s) = 2^s\zeta(s).$$

Note that both Dirichlet series on the left-hand side converge for $\Re(s) > 1$ since the sequence $(t_n)_{n \geq 0}$ takes only finitely many values.

We shall now give two proofs of this identity. The first uses Corollary 1, while the second relies on index-splitting (used also within the context of the Woods-Robbins product by Allouche, Mendès France and Peyrière [5], for instance).

Proof 1 of Theorem 1. We take Corollary 1 with $u(s) = 2^s + 1$ and $v(s) = 2^s - 1$. The proof immediately follows. \square

Of course, we could also prove the Theorem above without having recourse to any of the results above. For instance, we could simply use the relations $t_{2n} = t_n$ and $t_{2n+1} = 1 - t_n$ as follows.

Proof 2 of Theorem 1. We begin by splitting $\gamma(s)$ and $\varphi(s)$ into odd and even indexes. On the one hand, we have

$$\gamma(s) = 2^{-s}\gamma(s) - \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{t_n}{(2n + 1)^s} + (1 - 2^{-s})\zeta(s).$$

On the other hand,

$$\varphi(s) = 2^{-s}\zeta(s) - 2^{-s}\varphi(s) + \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{t_n}{(2n + 1)^s}.$$

Now taking the sum of these two equations yields

$$\gamma(s) + \varphi(s) = 2^{-s}(\gamma(s) - \varphi(s)) + \zeta(s),$$

and a simple rearrangement of the terms concludes this proof. \square

Here we note that whenever $t_{n-1} = t_n = 0$, the corresponding n^{th} term disappears from both Dirichlet series on the left-hand side. The first few missing terms are thus $n = 6, 10, 18, 24, \dots$ (sequence A248056 in the OEIS). Our result above implies several interesting examples, which we have already mentioned in the introduction.

Example 1. We have the following equalities:

$$(a) \quad \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{5t_{n-1} + 3t_n}{n^2} = \frac{2\pi^2}{3},$$

$$(b) \quad \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{9t_{n-1} + 7t_n}{n^3} = 8\zeta(3).$$

There are several ways to extend these results, which we will do in the following sections.

2.1. Generalization to Different Alphabets Along the Thue-Morse Sequence

In the following paragraphs, we extend Theorem 1 to linear combinations of series involving various alphabets $\{a, b\}$ along the Thue-Morse sequence, i.e., sequences with the substitutions $0 \rightarrow a$ and $1 \rightarrow b$, with $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$, over the t_n sequence. In particular, we show that there exist alphabets which give rise to identities involving the alternating zeta function $\eta(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s}$, others that give rise to identities involving the Riemann zeta function and, finally, alphabets that produce simple linear combinations with other Dirichlet series.

Theorem 2. Let $k, \ell > 0$ be real numbers and define the sequences $q_n = t_n - k$ and $r_n = t_n + \ell$ for all $n > 0$. Furthermore, consider the function $\lambda(s; k, \ell) = 2^s - (2^s(k - \ell) + (k + \ell))$ for some complex s with $\Re(s) > 1$. We then have

$$(1) \quad \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{q_{n-1}}{n^s} = \frac{1 - 2^s}{1 + 2^s} \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{r_n}{n^s} \quad \text{if } \lambda(s; k, \ell) = 0,$$

$$(2) \quad (2^s + 1) \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{q_{n-1}}{n^s} + (2^s - 1) \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{r_n}{n^s} = 2^s \zeta(s) \quad \text{if } \lambda(s; k, \ell) = 2^s,$$

$$(3) \quad (2^s + 1) \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{q_{n-1}}{n^s} + (2^s - 1) \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{r_n}{n^s} = 2^s \eta(s) \quad \text{if } \lambda(s; k, \ell) = 2^s - 2.$$

Proof. Define the sequences $q_n = t_n - k$ and $r_n = t_n + \ell$ for all $n > 0$ and real $k, \ell > 0$. We immediately have

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{q_{n-1}}{n^s} = \varphi(s) - k\zeta(s), \quad \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{r_n}{n^s} = \gamma(s) + l\zeta(s).$$

Thus,

$$(2^s + 1) \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{q_{n-1}}{n^s} + (2^s - 1) \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{r_n}{n^s} = \zeta(s) (2^s - (2^s(k - \ell) + (k + \ell))).$$

Inspired by the coefficient of $\zeta(s)$ on the right-hand side, we define the function $\lambda(s; k, \ell) = 2^s - (2^s(k - \ell) + (k + \ell))$ for real $k, \ell > 0$ and complex s with $\Re(s) > 1$. It is obvious that if $\lambda(s; k, \ell) = 0$, the $\zeta(s)$ term on the right-hand side vanishes, thus proving (1). If $\lambda(s; k, \ell) = 2^s$, we have identities of the same type as in Theorem 1, proving (2), and if $\lambda(s; k, \ell) = 2^s - 2$ then the identity $\eta(s) = (1 - 2^{1-s}) \zeta(s)$ quickly establishes (3). \square

Solutions to each of these cases lead to interesting illustrative examples. A first set of “simple” solutions – in terms of k and ℓ only – are easy to find. For the case (1) above, we have $k = \frac{1}{2}, \ell = -\frac{1}{2}$, which leads to the classic Woods-Robbins product by differentiation of the resulting series identity at $s = 0$, as already noted by Allouche and Cohen [3]. The solution of the second case, $k = 0, \ell = 0$, results in our identity in Theorem 1, and finally that of the third case ($k = 1, \ell = 1$) results in

$$(2^s + 1) \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{q_{n-1}}{n^s} + (2^s - 1) \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{r_n}{n^s} = 2^s \eta(s),$$

where $q_n \rightarrow \{-1, 0\}$ and $r_n \rightarrow \{1, 2\}$ along the Thue-Morse sequence.

Another, perhaps more interesting set of solutions can be found by taking s into account as well.

Proposition 1. *Define the sequences $q_n = t_n - k$ and $r_n = t_n + \ell$ for all $n > 0$ and real $k, \ell > 0$. We have the following equalities:*

$$\begin{aligned} (a) \quad & 5 \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{q_{n-1}}{n^2} = -3 \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{r_n}{n^2}, & q_n &\rightarrow \{-1, 0\}, r_n \rightarrow \left\{ \frac{1}{3}, \frac{4}{3} \right\} \\ (b) \quad & \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{9q_{n-1} + 7r_n}{n^3} = 8\zeta(3), & q_n &\rightarrow \{-1, 0\}, r_n \rightarrow \left\{ \frac{9}{7}, \frac{16}{7} \right\} \\ (c) \quad & \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{17q_{n-1} + 15r_n}{n^4} = 16\eta(4), & q_n &\rightarrow \{-\sqrt{2}, 1 - \sqrt{2}\}, \\ & & r_n &\rightarrow \left\{ \frac{17\sqrt{2} - 2}{15}, \frac{17\sqrt{2} + 13}{15} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The general solution of the equation $\lambda(s; k, \ell) = 0$ (i.e., case (1) in Theorem 2) in the reals is

$$s = \frac{\log\left(\frac{k+\ell}{-k+\ell+1}\right)}{\log 2},$$

with $k \neq \ell + 1$ and $k + \ell \neq 0$. So for instance we can take $k = 1$ and $\ell = \frac{1}{3}$, yielding the sequences $q_n = t_n - 1$ and $r_n = t_n + \frac{1}{3}$, for all $n \geq 0$, i.e., the sequences

defined respectively by $\{-1, 0\}$ and $\{\frac{1}{3}, \frac{4}{3}\}$ along the Thue-Morse sequence. A simple substitution above gives $s = 2$, thereby proving our statement (a).

We now turn our attention to the solution of $\lambda(s; k, \ell) = 2^s$ (i.e., case (2) in Theorem 2), which in the reals is

$$s = \frac{\log\left(-\frac{k+\ell}{k-\ell}\right)}{\log 2},$$

with $k - \ell \neq 0$ and $k + \ell \neq 0$. Let now $q_n = t_n - 1$ and $r_n = t_n + \frac{9}{7}$, for all $n \geq 0$, in other words the sequences defined respectively by $\{-1, 0\}$ and $\{\frac{9}{7}, \frac{16}{7}\}$ along the Thue-Morse sequence. This means that we have $k = 1$ and $\ell = \frac{9}{7}$, which yields $s = 3$ in the equation above and thus proves statement (b).

Finally, the solution of the equation $\lambda(s; k, \ell) = 2^s - 2$ in the reals, corresponding to case (3) in Theorem 2 is

$$s = \frac{\log\left(-\frac{k+\ell-2}{k-\ell}\right)}{\log 2},$$

with $k - \ell \neq 0$ and $k + \ell \neq 2$, which allows us to choose $k = \sqrt{2}$ and $\ell = \frac{17\sqrt{2}-2}{15}$. This gives the sequences $q_n = t_n - \sqrt{2}$ and $r_n = t_n + \frac{17\sqrt{2}-2}{15}$, for all $n \geq 0$, i.e., the sequences defined respectively by $\{-\sqrt{2}, 1 - \sqrt{2}\}$ and $\{\frac{17\sqrt{2}-2}{15}, \frac{17\sqrt{2}+13}{15}\}$ along the Thue-Morse sequence. Thus we have $s = 4$ and identity (c) as claimed. \square

3. Conclusion and Further Work

In this paper we have found closed forms for certain linear combinations of Dirichlet series associated with the Thue-Morse sequence in terms of known constants and functions. However, closed forms for the individual series remain elusive.

Question 1. Do the series $\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{t_n}{n^s}$ and $\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{t_{n-1}}{n^s}$ for $s \in \mathbb{C}$ with $\Re(s) > 1$ admit closed forms in terms of known constants and functions?

Despite our efforts, we have not been able to find a set of linear combinations allowing us to eliminate either f or g from Theorem 1.

3.1. Extension to Other Sequences

In some of our proofs we used an index-splitting method to find expressions for series involving the Thue-Morse sequence and variations thereof. The same method can possibly be applied to other series whose coefficients are generated by finite automata. A few examples are listed below, and the proofs are left to the reader.

Example 2. Let $\delta_n = t_n - t_{n-1}$ for all $n \geq 1$ and $\varepsilon_n = (-1)^{t_n}$ the ± 1 Thue-Morse sequence. Then for all s with $\Re(s) > 1$,

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\delta_n}{n^s} = \frac{4^s}{4^s - 1} \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{\varepsilon_n}{(2n+1)^s}.$$

Example 3. Let σ_n denote the “period-doubling sequence” (A096268 in the OEIS), defined by the recurrence $\sigma_{2n} = 0, \sigma_{4n+1} = 1, \sigma_{4n+3} = \sigma_n$. Then for all s with $\Re(s) > 1$,

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\sigma_n ((4n+3)^s - n^s)}{(4n^2 + 3n)^s} = 4^{-s} \zeta\left(s, \frac{1}{4}\right),$$

where $\zeta(s, a)$ denotes the Hurwitz zeta function.

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